

Assessment of The Determinants of Patients' Satisfaction with Nursing Care Received in Selected General Hospitals in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

Nursing is conferred with the responsibility of providing quality care at every level of health service delivery. Nurses' major contest is how to ensure that quality nursing service is delivered to all patients to gain patients' trust and satisfaction. This study assessed the determinants of patients' satisfaction with nursing care from patients who had received care during hospitalization in selected general hospitals of Ondo state. The study is a cross-sectional descriptive study. The study was carried out in nine selected general hospitals using Multi-stage random sampling technique to recruit 243 patients as participants. A self-structured Questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The questionnaire consists of four sections with reliability coefficient ranging from 0.819 to 0.923. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics. Findings revealed that 146 respondents representing 34.5% had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing care received. The strongest factor determining patients' satisfaction with nursing care was revealed to be health talk with average weighted mean of 3.18 followed by nursing care (3.02), hospital environment (2.51), discharge practices and aftercare (2.39), admission procedure (2.33) and patient autonomy (1.85). The study concluded that health

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talk, nursing care and hospital environment are the major factors determining patients' satisfaction with nursing care. Therefore, nurses should be more present in care by developing active listening skills and be sensitive to patients' needs.

Keywords: Nursing Care, Nurses Caring Attitude, Patients' Satisfaction, Determinant factors,

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Introduction

Patients' satisfaction with nursing care is seen as the level at which patients' desired needs, expectations, goals and preferences are accomplished through their interaction with nurses, other health care providers, and the care rendered. The important competitive benefit of nursing care is to make quality care available to patients (Findik & Unsar, 2015). The need for better nursing care that meet with patient's expectation has been recognized via health-related information and advances in technology, changes in expectations and views about nursing care, an increase in individuals' participation in issues regarding their health and increased cost and competitiveness in the health sector (Blasdell, 2017).

Joshi, Purani and Kartha (2013) viewed nursing care as an important aspect of caring process and as basic human attribute, directed towards providing better outcome, while Blasdell (2017) believed that caring is the moral centre of Nursing. Modern nursing care is gradually identifying the importance of awareness and satisfaction of patients in the provision of nursing care. Internationally, efficient responsiveness to patients' satisfaction is important to the success of nursing practice (Karaca & Durna, 2019).

Patient satisfaction is the patients' opinion of care in relation to care expected from nurses. It comprises technical, professional and social aspects of the caregiver as well as the care receiver. Also, it stands as the essential indicator of high-quality health care and it is used for the assessment and arrangement of health care (Lyngkhai & Brindha, 2015). Being an important indicator of high-quality health care, it can be said that there is a positive relationship between patient's satisfaction and nursing care. Thomas, et al., (2018) investigated how to increase patient satisfaction with multidimensional nursing approaches. They gathered data by employing two scales comprising of patient's satisfaction and nursing approaches and the findings of the research showed that multiple factors the affect the care provided by nurses improved patients' satisfaction with nursing care.

Assessing patients on what they think about the care and treatment they are receiving is an important process towards improvement of the quality of care which assists to ensure that the health services are meeting patients' needs and expectations. It may also help to recognize possible barriers to the delivery of services (Al Qahtani & Al Dahi, 2015). According to Ogunfowakun and Mora (2017), understanding the determinants of satisfaction is vital when developing effective involvements that can increase patients' satisfaction, which may in turn, improve other health related consequences and reduce re-hospitalisation. Despite numerous inconsistencies among the findings of these studies, there is a general agreement that satisfaction is determined by factors that can be characterised as endogenous (structure, process and outcome of care) or exogenous (patients' characteristics) towards the nursing care being received.

A number of research works have been done to examine how satisfied or dissatisfied patients/clients reported their feelings regarding nursing care both at regional and national levels, but few studies were conducted in assessing the factors responsible for patients' satisfaction level, especially within southwest Nigeria and particularly among the hospitals in Ondo State. For instance, Chawani, (2009), in his work conducted in Johannesburg, South Africa studied the interpretation of the factors leading patient's satisfaction with nursing care,

the experiences, views and expectations of nursing care of adult patients in hospitals across the globe, but the level of patients' satisfaction was not indicated.

It can be deduced from the above research works that there are necessities to know the factors that determine patients' satisfaction because there are few studies on the context of determinants despite numerous studies on nursing care and patients' satisfaction, the researcher noticed that there was paucity of studies that examined factors associated with patients' satisfaction with nursing care in Ondo State and across Nigeria. Thus, the interest of the researcher was to fill the vacuum by assessing the determinants of patients' satisfaction with nursing care. The viewpoints of patient's related determinants, nurse's related determinants and facility related determinants are used to assess these in selected general hospitals in Ondo State. Also, there is a need to critically study the caring attitude of nurses expected by patients.

Thus, the main objective of this study was to determine factors responsible for patients' satisfaction on nursing care received in selected general hospitals in Ondo State. This study specifically:

1. examined the factors determining the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care in selected general hospital in Ondo State;
2. determined the influence of caring attitude of nurses as observed by patients regarding their level of satisfaction with nursing care in selected general hospital in Ondo state; and
3. assessed the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care received in selected general hospitals in Ondo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study:

1. What are the factors determining the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care in selected general hospitals in Ondo State?
2. What are caring attitude of nurses as observed by patients regarding their level of satisfaction with nursing care in selected general hospitals in Ondo state?
3. What is the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care received in selected general hospitals in Ondo State?

Methodology

A cross-sectional descriptive design was used to assess determinants of patients' satisfaction with nursing care in selected general hospitals in Ondo State. The study was conducted in selected General Hospitals in Ondo State. The study focused on in-patients who had spent at least five days receiving healthcare in each of the healthcare facilities or discharged home but on an appointment visit to clinics in the selected facilities. The study focused on patients aged 18-60 years and who have recuperated enough to be able to accurately report their satisfaction with the nursing care received in the healthcare facilities. The total number of in-patients in Ondo State General Hospitals was estimated to be about 5,000 (Ondo State Ministry of Health, 2020).

The sample size was determined using a Cochran's formula for sample size determination, thus 243 respondents were used so as to give room for inappropriate filled and unreturned questionnaire. This study adopted a multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument for data

collection was a self-structured questionnaire derived from literature review. The questionnaire consisted of 62 items divided into sections A to C. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity. The items in the questionnaire were presented to experts in the test and measurement, in nursing field and the supervisor for review, correction and appraisal after which necessary corrections were made. Reliability was done using pre-test method where the developed questionnaire was administered to 10% of total population in a different general hospital for about 24 respondents to ascertain that it is testing what it is set to test. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for patients' satisfaction with nursing care is 0.849, factors determining patients' satisfaction with nursing care is 0.720, and while for caring attitude expected of a Nurse is 0.841.

The data for this study were gathered through primary source. The researcher, with the help of two research assistants, administered questionnaires to the respondents who were required to provide responses to the questions therein. The descriptive analysis was employed to answer the developed research question for this study,

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care in selected general hospitals in Ondo State?

Table 1: Patients' satisfaction with nursing care N= 229

S/N	ITEMS	Excellent (%)	Good (%)	Fair (%)	Poor (%)	Mean
1.	<i>Information You Were Given:</i> How clear and complete the nurses' explanations were about tests, treatments and what to expect	20 (8.7)	107 (46.7)	93 (40.6)	9 (3.9)	2.60
2.	<i>Instructions:</i> How well nurses explained how to prepare for tests and operations	11 (4.8)	111 (48.5)	92 (40.2)	15 (6.6)	2.52
3.	<i>Ease of Getting Information:</i> Willingness of nurses to answer your questions	9 (3.9)	127 (55.5)	87 (38.0)	6 (2.6)	2.61
4.	<i>Information Given by Nurses:</i> How well nurses communicated with patients, families, and doctors	5 (2.2)	130 (56.8)	88 (38.4)	6 (2.6)	2.59
5.	<i>Informing Family or Friends:</i> How well the nurses kept them informed about your condition and needs	19 (8.3)	118 (51.5)	76 (33.2)	16 (7.0)	2.61
6.	<i>Involving Family or Friends in Your Care:</i> How much they were allowed to help in your care	61 (26.6)	142 (62.0)	26 (11.4)	0 (0.0)	3.15
7.	<i>Concern and Caring by Nurses:</i> Courtesy and respect you were given; friendliness and kindness	5 (2.2)	153 (66.8)	61 (26.6)	10 (4.4)	2.67
8.	<i>Attention of Nurses to Your Condition:</i>	27	138	54	10 (4.4)	2.79

	How often nurses checked on you and how well they kept track of how you were doing	(11.8)	(60.3)	(23.6)		
9.	<i>Observation:</i> How well do they keep track of how you are doing?	25 (10.9)	142 (62.0)	47 (20.5)	15 (6.6)	2.77
10.	<i>Recognition of Your Opinions:</i> How much nurses ask you what you think is important and give you choices	11 (4.8)	68 (29.7)	118 (51.5)	32 (14.0)	2.25
11.	<i>Consideration of Your Needs:</i> Willingness of the nurses to be flexible in meeting your needs	18 (7.9)	86 (37.6)	104 (45.4)	21 (9.2)	2.44
12.	<i>The Daily Routine of the Nurses:</i> How well they adjusted their schedules to your needs	34 (14.8)	131 (57.2)	59 (25.8)	5 (2.2)	2.85
13.	<i>Helpfulness:</i> Ability of the nurses to make you comfortable and reassure you	71 (31.0)	145 (63.3)	13 (5.7)	0 (0.0)	3.25
14.	<i>Nursing Staff Response to Your Calls:</i> How quick they were to help	98 (42.8)	114 (49.8)	12 (5.2)	5 (2.2)	3.33
15.	<i>Skill and Competence of Nurses:</i> How well things were done, like giving medicine and handling IVs	70 (30.6)	128 (55.9)	26 (11.4)	5 (2.2)	3.15
16.	<i>Coordination of Care:</i> The teamwork between nurses and other hospital staff who took care of you	20 (8.7)	130 (56.8)	68 (29.7)	11 (4.8)	2.69
17.	<i>Restful Atmosphere Provided by Nurses:</i> Amount of peace and quiet	16 (7.0)	118 (51.5)	89 (38.9)	6 (2.6)	2.63
18.	<i>Privacy:</i> Provisions for your privacy by nurses	24 (10.5)	138 (60.3)	56 (24.5)	11 (4.8)	2.76
19.	<i>Discharge Instructions:</i> How clearly and completely the nurses told you what to do and what to expect when you left the hospital	26 (11.4)	110 (48.0)	83 (36.2)	10 (4.4)	2.66
20.	<i>Coordination of Care After Discharge:</i> Nurses' efforts to provide for your needs after you left the hospital.	10 (4.4)	68 (29.7)	116 (50.7)	35 (15.3)	2.23

Table 1 revealed the level of satisfaction the patients had with nursing care services. 20(8.7%) had excellent information given to them on tests results and what to expect, 107(46.7%) had good information, 93(40.6%) had fair information, 9(3.9%) had poor information. 11(4.8%) of the respondents submitted nurses gave excellent instructions on how to prepare for tests and procedures, 111(48.5%) said they had good instructions,

92(40.2%) said they had fair instructions while 15(6.6%) had poor instructions. On ease of getting information 9(3.9%) had excellent ease of getting information, 127(55.5%) had good ease of getting information, 87(38%) had fair ease of getting information from nurses while 6(2.6%) had poor information. 5(2.2%) communicated with nurses, patient, families and doctors excellently, 130(56.8%) had good satisfaction on information given by nurses, 88(38.4%) had fair satisfaction while 6(2.6%) had poor satisfaction on information. 19(8.3%) of the respondents submitted the nurses excellent way of informing their family and friends about their condition and needs, 118(51.5%) gave good remark while 76(33.2%) gave fair remark, 16(7%) gave poor remark. 61(26.6%) gave excellent remark to nurses for how much they allowed friends and family in their care, 142(62.0) gave good remark, while 26(11.4%) gave fair remark.

Also, 5(2.2%) submitted excellent concern and care by nurses, 153(66.8%) gave good remark on the concern and care by nurses, 61(26.6%) gave fair remark while 10(4.4%) of the respondents gave poor remark. 27(11.8%) gave excellent remark on how often nurses check on them and kept track of how they were doing, 138(60.3%) gave good remark, 54(23.6%) gave fair remark while 10(4.4%) gave poor remark. On how observant nurses are, 25(10.9%) submitted nurses were excellent observers, 142(62%) gave good remarks, 47(20.5%) gave fair remarks while 15(6.6%) gave poor remarks. On how much nurses recognise opinion of patients, 11(4.8%) gave excellent recognition of opinions, 68(29.7%) gave good recognition of opinion, 118(51.5%) gave fair remarks while 32(14%) gave poor remarks.

On willingness of nurses to be flexible in meeting patients needs, 18(7.9%) gave excellent consideration of needs, 86(37.6%) gave good consideration of needs, 104(45.4%) gave fair remarks and 21(9.2%) gave poor remarks. On daily routine of nurses, 34(14.8%) gave excellent remark, 131(57.2%) gave good remark, 59(25.8%) gave fair remark while 5(2.2%) gave poor remark. On Nursing staff response to patient's call, 94(42.8%) gave excellent response, 114(49.8%) gave good responses, 12(5.2%) gave fair response while 5(2.2%) gave poor response. On skill and competence of nurses, 70(30.6%) gave excellent response, 128(55.9%) gave good response, 26(11.4%) gave fair response while 5(2.2%) gave poor response. On coordination of care, 20(8.7%) of respondents gave excellent remarks, 130(56.8%) gave good remarks, 68(29.7%) gave fair remarks while 11(4.8%) gave poor remarks. 16(7%) submitted nurses gave excellent restful atmosphere, 118(51.5%) submitted good restful atmosphere, 89(38.9%) submitted fair atmosphere while 6(2.6%) gave poor remarks. 24(10.5%) said privacy provision by nurses was excellent, 138(60.3%) submitted good provision of privacy, 56(24.5%) gave fair provision while 11(4.8%) gave poor remark. On clear discharge instructions from nurses, 26(11.4%) gave excellent remark, 110(48%) gave good remark, 83(36.2%) gave fair remark, 10(4.4%) gave poor remark. On coordination of care after discharge, 10(4.4%) gave excellent remark, 68(29.7%) gave good remark, 116(50.7%) gave fair remark while 35(15.3%).

To compute the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care services in selected general hospitals, the following method was used

Mean = 54.55

SD = 2.98

Min = 48

Max = 60

$\bar{X} - SD = 54.55 - 2.98 = 51.57$

$\bar{X} + SD = 54.55 + 2.98 = 57.53$

Range

Scores from 48 - 51 low level

52 - 57 moderate level

58 - 60 high level

Table 2: Level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care/

Level	Frequency	Percent
Poor	42	18.3
Fair	67	29.2
Good	79	34.5
Excellent	41	17.9
Total	229	100.0

Table 2 summarises the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care services. From the table, 42 respondents representing 18.3 percent had low level of satisfaction with nursing care services, 146 respondents representing 63.8 percent had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing care services while 41 respondents representing 17.9 percent had high level of satisfaction with nursing care services. It could be concluded that most of the patients had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing care services.

Research Question 2: What are the factors determining the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care in selected general hospitals of Ondo state?

Table 3: Factors determining patients' satisfaction with nursing care N= 229

S/N	ITEMS	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Mean
Admission Procedure						
1.	Information are provided to you by nurse during admission	11 (4.8)	49 (21.4)	110 (48.0)	59 (25.8)	2.05
2.	The manner of reception at the ward is satisfactory	22 (9.6)	90 (39.3)	99 (43.2)	18 (7.9)	2.51
3.	The waiting time to access nursing care service is moderate	31 (13.5)	67 (29.3)	93 (40.6)	38 (16.6)	2.40
4.	The registration process is satisfactory	21 (9.2)	90 (39.3)	63 (27.5)	55 (24.0)	2.34
Nursing Care						
5.	The nursing staff have adequate expertise	45 (19.7)	176 (76.9)	8 (3.5)	0 (0)	3.16
6.	Nurses usually help patients whenever they are asked for help	63 (27.5)	141 (61.6)	25 (10.9)	0 (0)	3.17
7.	The way nurses treated patients on admission is adequate	57 (24.9)	121 (52.8)	51 (22.3)	0 (0)	3.03
8.	Satisfaction with the care and concern shown by nurses is satisfactory	27 (11.8)	114 (49.8)	88 (38.4)	0 (0)	2.73
Health Talk						
9.	The nurses are very clear with explanations about treatment	24 (10.5)	167 (72.9)	38 (16.6)	0 (0)	2.94
10.	The hospital staff are approachable to ask questions	62 (27.1)	156 (68.1)	11 (4.8)	0 (0)	3.22
11.	The manner with which answers are provided is encouraging	135 (59.0)	94 (41.0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.59
12.	The amount of information gotten is very adequate	100 (43.7)	128 (55.9)	1 (0.4)	0 (0)	3.43
13.	The information gotten from nurses are clear	12 (5.2)	147 (64.2)	59 (25.8)	11 (4.8)	2.70
Hospital Environment						
14.	The hospital environment is very clean	23 (10)	103 (45)	95 (41.5)	8 (3.5)	2.62
15.	The condition (comfort, privacy etc.) of the consulting room is satisfactory	0(0)	120 (52.4)	79 (34.5)	30 (13.1)	2.39

Patient Autonomy						
16.	The patient is allowed to participate in treatment decisions	0 (0)	30 (13.1)	154 (67.2)	45 (19.7)	1.93
17.	Patients are encouraged to be self-sufficient	0 (0)	22 (9.6)	133 (58.1)	74 (32.3)	1.77
Discharge and Aftercare						
18.	Adequate information are provided whenever there is need to transfer any patient	0 (0)	85 (37.1)	132 (57.6)	12 (5.2)	2.32
19.	Information are provided regarding further treatment	0 (0)	98 (42.8)	119 (52.0)	12 (5.2)	2.38
20.	The timing of discharge from the hospital is satisfactory	10 (4.4)	105 (45.9)	102 (44.5)	12 (5.2)	2.49
21.	Patients are always willing to recommend this hospital to others	11 (4.8)	82 (35.8)	111 (48.5)	25 (10.9)	2.35

Table 3 revealed factors determining patient's satisfaction in nursing care services. On information provided by the nurse during admission, 11(4.8%) strongly agreed, 49(21.4%) agreed, 110(48%) disagreed, while 59 (25.8%). The manner of reception at the ward is satisfactory as strongly agreed by 22(9.6%) respondents, 90(39.3%) agreed, 99(43.2%) disagreed while 18(7.9%) strongly disagreed. 57(24.9%) respondents strongly agreed the way nurses treated patients on admission is adequate, 121(52.8%) agreed while 51(22.3%) disagreed. 21(9.2%) of the respondents submitted registration process is satisfactory, 90(39.3%) agreed, 63(27.5%) disagreed, 55(24%) strongly disagreed. 45(19.7%) strongly agreed nursing staff have adequate expertise, 176(76.9%) agreed while 8(3.5%) disagreed. 63(27.5%) strongly agreed nurses usually help patients whenever they asked for help, 141(61.6%) agreed while 25(10.9%) disagreed. 27(11.8%) strongly agreed satisfaction with the care and concern shown by nurses, 114(49.8%) agreed while 88 (38.4%). 24 (10.5%) strongly agreed nurses are very clear with explanations about treatment, 167 (72.9%) agreed while 38(16.6%) disagreed. 62 (27.1%) strongly agreed the hospital, 156 (68.1%) agreed while 11(4.8%). 135(59%) strongly agreed the manner with which answers are provided is encouraging while 94 (41%) agreed. 100(43.7%) strongly agreed the amount of information is very adequate, 128(55.9%) agreed while 1(0.4%) disagreed.

Also, 12(5.2%) strongly agreed the information gotten from nurses are clear, 147(64.2%) agreed, 59(25.8%) disagreed while 11(4.8%) strongly disagreed. 23(10%) strongly agreed the hospital environment is very clean, 103(45%) agreed, 95(41.5%) disagreed, 8(3.5%) strongly disagreed. 120(52.4%) agreed the condition of the consulting room is satisfactory, 79(34.5%) disagreed while 30(13.1%) strongly disagreed. 30(13.1%) agreed the patient is allowed to participate in treatment decisions, 154(67.2%) disagreed while 45(19.7%) strongly disagreed. 22(9.6%) agreed patients are encouraged to be self-sufficient, 133(58.1%) disagreed while 74(32.3%) strongly disagreed. 85(37.1%) agreed adequate information are provided whenever there is need to transfer any patient, 132(57.6%) agreed while 12(5.2%). 85(37.1%) agreed adequate information are provided whenever there is

need to transfer any patient, 132(57.6%) disagreed while 12(5.2%) strongly disagreed. 98(42.8%) agreed information are provided, 119(52%) disagreed while 12(5.2%) strongly disagreed. 10(4.4%) strongly agreed the timing of discharge from the hospital is satisfactory, 105(45.9%) agreed, 102(44.5%) disagreed while 12(5.2%) strongly disagreed. 11(4.8%) strongly agreed patients are willing to recommend the hospital to others, 82(35.8%) agreed, 111(48.%) disagreed while 25(10.9%) strongly disagreed.

Table 4: Summary of Factors determining patients' satisfaction with nursing care N= 229

FACTORS	Average Weighted Mean	Rank
Admission Procedure	2.33	5 th
Nursing Care	3.02	2 nd
Health Talk	3.18	1 st
Hospital Environment	2.51	3 rd
Patient Autonomy	1.85	6 th
Discharge and Aftercare	2.39	4 th

Mean Cut-Off: 2.50

Table 4 revealed the average weighted mean of factors determining patients' satisfaction with nursing care services. Admission procedure had an average weighted mean of 2.33, nursing care had 3.02, health talk had 3.18, hospital environment had 2.51, patient autonomy had 1.85 while discharge and aftercare had 2.39. It could be concluded that health talk, nursing care and hospital environment are the major factors determining patients' satisfaction with nursing care services.

Research Question 3: What caring attitude nurses are expected by patients in selected general hospitals of Ondo state?

Table 5: Caring attitude of nurses expected by patients N= 229

S/N	ITEMS	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Mean
1.	Attentively listen to patient	141 (61.6)	78 (34.1)	10 (4.4)	0 (0)	3.57
2.	Give instruction on care to patient	113 (49.3)	106 (46.3)	10 (4.4)	0 (0)	3.45
3.	Treat patient as an individual	106 (46.3)	123 (53.7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.46
4.	Demonstrate professional knowledge and skill	113 (49.3)	104 (45.4)	12 (5.2)	0 (0)	3.44
5.	Respond quickly to patients' call	119 (52.0)	100 (43.7)	10 (4.4)	0 (0)	3.48
6.	Be honest with patient	135 (59.0)	94 (41.0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.59
7.	Encourage patient to verbalize fear	113 (49.3)	116 (50.7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.49
8.	Provide a reassurance presence	119 (52.0)	110 (48.0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.52
9.	Be empathetic with patient	116 (50.7)	113 (49.3)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.51

10.	Be sensitive to patients' feeling and mood	115 (50.2)	114 (49.8)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.50
11.	Affectionately relate to the patient	99 (43.2)	118 (51.5)	12 (5.2)	0 (0)	3.38
12.	Respect patient belief	111 (48.5)	106 (46.3)	12 (5.2)	0 (0)	3.43

Table 5 showed 141(61.6%) respondents strongly agreed nurses attentively listened to patient, 78(34.1%) agreed, 10(4.4%) disagreed while none strongly disagreed. 113(49.3%) respondents strongly agreed nurses give instruction on care to patients, 106(46.3%) agreed while 10(4.4%) disagreed. 106(46.3%) respondents strongly agreed nurses treats patient as individuals while 123(53.7) only agreed. 113(49.3%) respondents strongly agreed nurses demonstrate professional knowledge and skill, 104 (45.4%) agreed while 12(5.2%) disagreed. 119(52%) strongly agreed nurses respond quickly to patient's call, 100(43.7%) agreed, while 10(4.4%) disagreed. 135(59%) respondents strongly agreed nurses are honest with patients while 94(41%) agreed. 113(49.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed nurses encourage patient to verbalize fear, while 116(50.7%) agreed. 119(52%) respondents strongly agreed nurses provide a reassurance presence while 110(48%) agreed. 116(50.7%) respondents strongly agreed nurses are empathetic with patient, while 113(49.3%) agreed. 115(50.2%) strongly agreed nurses are sensitive to patients feelings and mood while 114(49.8%) agreed. 99(43.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed nurses affectionately relate to their patients, 118(51.5%) agreed while 12(5.2%) disagreed. 111(48.5%) of the respondents strongly agreed nurses respect patients belief, 106(46.3%) agreed while 12(5.2%) disagreed.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the result revealed that 42 respondents representing 18.3 percent had low level of satisfaction with nursing care, 146 respondents representing 63.8 percent had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing care while 41 respondents representing 17.9 percent had high level of satisfaction with nursing care. It was revealed that most of the patients had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing care.

Patients' satisfaction level is an indicator for evaluating quality of health service (Kingdon & Newman, 2013; Mishra & Gupta, 2012). Patient satisfaction is an important component of the health care industry in this competitive modern era. It is used as an important indicator of quality care and is frequently included in healthcare planning and evaluation (Akhtari-Zavare, Abdullah, Hassan, Said, & Kamali, 2017). They concluded that in most cases, patients do have moderate level of satisfaction with nursing care. Findik and Unsar (2015) measured patients satisfaction with access to care includes availability of service, technical quality of care, interpersonal care, communication and financing of care. They found an average level of satisfaction with nursing care. A study by Morris and Weiss (2015) among patients who underwent surgical patients revealed that slightly more than half (51.3%) of the patient were satisfied with the nursing care.

In contrast to this finding, Obemeyen (2017) showed that 57.1% of the patients had high satisfaction with nursing care. Otite and Ogionwo (2016) conducted a survey study of a random sample of 420 patients to determine the extent of patient satisfaction with care

provided. The extent of overall patient satisfaction with the quality of care provided at the hospital was found to be quite high (Excellent, 74.7%; Very good, 23.7%). Odetola, Muluemebet, Misra and Berheto (2016) revealed high levels of patient satisfaction, and the patient perception of nurses influenced the way the patient rated quality of nursing care.

Nursing care plays a major role in the health care services. The achievement of outstanding patient satisfaction and building a culture of client service distinction in hospitals is dependent on finding the intangible aspects of expectation that contribute to patient satisfaction. Assessing patients on what they think about the care and treatment they are receiving is an important process towards improvement of the quality of care which helps to ensure that the health services are meeting patients' needs.

The findings of the result showed that admission procedure had an average weighted mean of 2.33, nursing care had 3.02, health talk had 3.18, hospital environment had 2.51, patient autonomy had 1.85 while discharge and aftercare had 2.39. It was revealed that health talk, nursing care and hospital environment are the major factors determining patients' satisfaction with nursing care. In support of this finding, Al-Mailam (2015) found that nursing-staff services, hospital environment, physician issues, other staff and waiting-time are the key issues that drive satisfaction with the outpatient department.

Ogunfowakan and Mora (2017) identified the factors associated with patient satisfaction and dissatisfaction within hospital setting. They concluded that nursing care and hospital environment are the major factors determining patients' satisfaction.

Conclusion

Sequel to the findings of this study, it is concluded that most of the patients had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing care. The study also concluded that health talk, nursing care and hospital environment are the major factors determining patients' satisfaction with nursing care.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. If nursing care, health talk and hospital environment can be adequately improved; high level of the patients' satisfaction with nursing care can be achieved.
2. Continuous training of the nurses is recommended as it may improve their performance and consequently raise patients' satisfaction with nursing care.
3. Continuous monitoring of clients' satisfaction with all aspects of care could aid in improvement of the quality of services.
4. The hospital authorities should recruit more nurses, then, the nurses would be able to have more direct care. Consequently, the amount and the quality of nurse-patients' communication and opportunities for patient education would increase
5. Nurses should be more present in care by developing active listening skills and be sensitive to patients' needs

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